

SELECTIVE REINFORCEMENT OF THE HARD SEGMENT OF POLYURETHANE WITH GRAPHENE OXIDE

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1 Introduction

Polyurethane (PU), a multiblock copolymer, is well known for its two-phase microstructure containing alternative hard and soft segments. Due to special morphological arrangement of hard and soft domain segregation, it can exhibit very interesting thermal and mechanical properties. It has been revealed that the hard segment with glassy or laminar crystalline structure acts as a physical crosslinkers for the rubbery soft segment in PU. PU has been used for a variety of application such as adhesives, coating, fibers and biometric materials. Graphene, one atom thick two dimensional sheet of sp² hybridized carbon, is emerging as a new rising star in the field of material science [1]. Combining the unique properties of graphene with PU elastomer, we expect that PU/ Graphene nanocomposites can be used in the field of application where high performance is necessary [2,3].

Much work have focused on utilizing clay, carbon nanotube, graphene and graphene oxide (GO) as reinforcements to mechanically enhance performance of polymers [3,4,5,6]. One important parameter in the composite reinforcement is good dispersion of the filler. Another requirement for good mechanical reinforcement is good stress transfer leading to strong interfacial bonding [7]. For the interaction of GO with polymer chains, we would expect the grafting of GO with the matrix polymer to create a very strong interface. As for the dispersion and stress transfer requirements, GO is ideal for mechanical reinforcement. Furthermore, we note that the interaction with the matrix polymer will be very sensitive to the nature of the functional group. As such, great care must be taken when choosing the functional group (or grafted polymer chain) [4]. There are many reports on the reinforcement of PU with functionalized carbon nanotube, graphene and GO. Khan and his

coworkers prepared functionalized CNT based PU nanocomposites with tunable mechanical properties by targeted reinforcement of either hard or soft segment of PU [4]. There is a report on the polyurethane grafted single-walled carbon nanotubes that improved the dispersion of SWNT in the PU matrix and strengthen the interfacial interaction between the PU and SWNT [10]. Cai and his coworkers also reported the strong interaction of GO nanoplatelets with hard segment of PU by simple solution process, which allows effective load transfer [6]. Here, in our knowledge, we first time report the successful grafting of polyurethane on the graphene oxide surface and graphene sheet, became a part of hard segment. Furthermore, it is expected that the functional group present in GO can allow targeted insertion of the GO sheets into specific regions of the matrix. This can allow fine control over the properties of the final composite. As a result, our nanocomposites showed 138.5% increase of Young's modulus at 1 wt% and ~55% increase of the tensile strength at 0.5 wt% loading, significantly better than neat polyurethane.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Poly(tetramethylene ether glycol) (PTMEG, Average Mw: 2000 g/mol), 4,4'-methylene diphenyl diisocyanate (MDI) and 1,4-butanediol (BD) from Sigma Aldrich were used for in situ polymerization. Flake of synthetic graphite (> 20µm) was purchased from Aldrich. Graphene oxide (GO) was prepared by modified Hummer's Method [8,9]. Anhydrous Tetrahydrofuran (THF) from Sigma Aldrich was used as received.

2.2 Composite Processing

PTMEG and BD were dehydrated at 70°C under a vacuum for 24 hours and NCO content in MDI was

determined by back titration using dibutylamine. Colloidal suspension of graphene oxide in tetrahydrofuran (0.5 wt%) was prepared by sonicating for 0.5 hr and magnetic stirring for 3 days. The reactive site present in the GO for the reaction with MDI, was determined by back titration using dibutylamine. Then calculated amount of MDI was added to the suspension of graphene oxide and the mixture was well stirred at room temperature in nitrogen atmosphere for 4 hours. PTMEG was added and the mixture was continuously agitated at 65°C for 5 hours. The solvent was removed at 75°C and the chain extender, BD, was added to the prepolymer. Then the mixture was mixed at 1200rpm for 3 minutes and casted in preheated mold and cured at 90°C for 24 hrs. Here, the content of hard segment in PU is 37.1 % by weight.

2.3 Characterization Technique

Dimensions of the GO on freshly cleaved mica substrate were estimated with tapping-mode atomic force microscopy (AFM, Digital instruments Nanoscope). AFM sample was prepared by dispersing GO (0.1mg/ml) in pure water and sonication for 5 hours and drop casted on the mica surface. Morphological feature and lateral dimensions of GO was observed by field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM Hitachi Co., Tokyo, Japan). FESEM sample was prepared by dispersing 0.5 mg/ml GO in water and sonicated 5 hours and drop casted on silicon substrate and dried on the air. An X-ray diffractometer [Rigaku X-ray diffractometer (Rigaku, Japan) with Cu KR ($\lambda=1.540 \text{ \AA}$) radiation over a Bragg angle ranging from 5° to 45°] was used to measure XRD patterns of GO based PU nanocomposites. The microscopic features of composite were characterized by Transmission electron microscope (TEM; JSM-6400 Microscope, Japan). Composite was microtomed with a diamond knife at -90°C into $\sim 100 \text{ nm}$ thick slices and placed on Cu TEM grids. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was carried out on a DSC (TA industry, Q-20) with heating rate $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and cooling rate $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. All DSC measurements were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere. Tensile test of $\sim 2 \text{ mm}$ width specimens were carried out using universal testing machine (UTM) at a strain rate $500\text{mm}/\text{min}$. The flexural storage modulus (E') and dissipation

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the modification of GO with MDI and subsequent grafting of polyurethane on the surface of GO.

factor ($\tan \delta$) of the PU nanocomposites were determined via dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) using a TA instruments Q800 series DMA over a temperature range -100 to 120°C at a frequency of 1Hz , at a ramp rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

3 Results and Discussion

Figure 1 displays the schematic illustration of isocyanate modification of GO and subsequent grafting of polyurethane on the surface of GO. Here, MDI was mixed with GO suspension in THF and carried out the reaction at room temperature for 4 hours so that hydroxyl group of GO reacts with isocyanate group of MDI. Relative reactivity of remaining isocyanate group in MDI after reaction with GO in comparisons with fresh MDI is lower due to steric hindrance so that MDI grafted on the graphene oxide surface with remaining one isocyanate group free for the reaction with polyols

Figure 2. (a) Tapping mode AFM image of GO, and (c) corresponding height profile, (b) FESEM image of GO; scale bar 1 μm and (d) TEM image of 0.5 wt % GO dispersed PU; 200nm scale bar.

such as PTMEG can form prepolymer in two step process [10,11,12]. After the chain extension with 1,4-butanediol (BD) and curing at 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 hours, the nanocomposites was finally formed. AFM image of GO obtained by tapping mode is given in Figure 2 (a) and corresponding height profile in Figure 2 (c) reveals that the typical lateral size of GO is on the order of several hundred nanometers with thickness 0.6 to 0.8 nm in agreement with reports found in literature. The difference from the thickness value from the interlamellar spacing of GO determined by X-ray diffraction pattern, 0.7 nm, was negligible. FESEM image of GO in Figure 2 (b) displays the thin membranous structure. Morphological information of PU composites was obtained using TEM and XRD. TEM image of the 0.5 wt% of nanocomposite in figure 2(d) reveals that the GO sheets are embedded and well dispersed within the polyurethane. Interestingly GO sheets with PU appear extended and interconnected due to the chemical affinity with the matrix. XRD patterns of nanocomposites containing different wt% of GO are given in Figure 3 and lack reflections from layered nanoparticles indicating the fine dispersion

Figure 3. XRD patterns of (a) 0, (b) 0.3, (c) 0.5, (d) 1.0 wt% of GO based PU nanocomposites.

of GO in the form of nearly monolayer rather than agglomeration in polymer matrix. Furthermore,

graphene oxide sheet-matrix interaction is strong enough due to grafting reaction so, sheets cannot aggregate during the solvent evaporation stage. Figure 4 displays the DSC thermograms during heating and cooling cycles of PU nanocomposites. The melting temperature (T_m) of the hard segment of PU (168.9 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) increases at 0.5 wt% loading of GO (177.1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and further loading of GO resulted in decrease of T_m . In the cooling curve of PU/GO composites, large decrease of the crystallization temperature of the hard segment of PU from 164 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 71.6 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 1 wt% of GO was observed, indicating the functional group present in GO allowed targeted insertion of the graphene oxide sheets into hard segment of the matrix and retarded crystallization of hard segments. Figure 5 displays the effect of GO loading for the reinforcement of polyurethane elastomer. Both tensile strength and Young's modulus of PU increased with the addition of 0.5 wt% of GO. Further addition of GO up to 1.0 wt% shows decrease of the tensile strength. This may be due to the agglomeration of GO. The Flexural storage modulus, E' and loss tangent, $\tan \delta$ of PU containing GOs are shown in Figure 6. E' value of 0.5wt% GO/PU composite is about 14.7% higher than that of the PU at -85 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Slight shift in the

Figure 4. DSC thermograms during heating ($10^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$) (left) and cooling ($5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$), (right) cycles of PU nanocomposites containing different GO contents (wt%): (a) 0; (b) 0.3; (c) 0.5; (d) 1.0.

Figure 5. Stress –strain response of PU reinforced with (a) 0, (b) 0.3, (c) 0.5, (d) 1.0 wt% of GO.

peak temperatures of damping factor ($\tan \delta$) associated with the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the soft segment was observed, which reveals the weak interaction between the GO and the soft segment of PU. The decrease of the amplitude of $\tan \delta$ with increasing the GO content indicates the restriction of the motion of PU chains due to grafting reactions of the GO with isocyanate groups for PU chains [6,13]. The decrease in the elongation at break with increasing the GO content in tensile test of the composite is in agreement with DMA results with regards to the increase of rubbery plateau moduli. Hence, the GO affected the polyurethane by two ways. Grafting of MDI on the GO retarded the crystallization of the hard segment of PU and GO itself reinforced the PU matrix to increase the mechanical strength of nanocomposites.

Conclusion

We prepared composites from *in situ* polymerization of polyurethanes reinforced with GO. Grafting of

Figure 6. Flexural storage modulus, E' (left) and loss tangent $\tan \delta$ (right) of (a) 0, (b) 0.3, (c) 0.5 and (d) 1.0 wt% of GO based PU nanocomposites.

MDI on the GO by dispersing in tetrahydrofuran showed markedly altered the crystallization of the polyurethane hard segments. We interpreted this as evidence of selective insertion of GO sheets in hard segments depending on the surface chemistry of the GO and the chemical structure of the segment. This interpretation is supported by the DSC thermograms and mechanical properties of the composites. GO based composites tend to maintain their strength and elongation at higher GO loading. At certain concentration of GO in PU, GO become segregated in the hard segments and so enhance the modulus and tensile strength with significant value of elongation at break. This controlled reinforcement of the hard segment of PU has allowed us to prepare composites with 138.5 % increased in Young's modulus at 1 wt.% and ~55% increase of the tensile strength at 0.5 wt% loading, significantly higher than neat polyurethane.

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